

Numerical study of surface chemical reactions in 2D-FET based pH sensors

A. Toral-Lopez^{*,1}, E. G. Marin^{*}, J. Cuesta^{*}, F. G. Ruiz^{*}, F. Pasadas[†], A. Medina-Rull and A. Godoy^{*}

^{*}Departamento de Electrónica y Tecnología de Computadores, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Granada (Spain)

[†]Departament d'Enginyeria Electrònica, Escola d'Enginyeria, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Spain)

¹atoral@ugr.es

Abstract

This work numerically evaluates the impact of surface chemical reactions on the performance of 2D-FET based pH sensors. More precisely, we focus on the adsorption of chlorine ions and the expulsion of protons at the sensing interface of FET sensor. This analysis is performed through numerical simulations encompassing the modelling of both the semiconductor device and the liquid solution to be analysed. In the semiconductor region the 2D Poisson - 1D Continuity equations are self-consistently solved, while in the electrolyte region we deal with the modified Poisson - Boltzmann system [1]. The simulator also includes the interactions taking place at the electrolyte-sensing layer interface through: *i*) the non-constant profile of water permittivity, and *ii*) the steric effects in the ions concentration by introducing the Potentials of Mean Force (PMF) [2, 3]. This comprehensive description of the electrolyte-device interface provides a suitable framework to unveil the relevance of multiple chemical reactions, like the adsorption of chlorine ions, on the behaviour of 2D-FET based pH sensors.

I. Introduction

The Ion-Sensitive FET (ISFET) was introduced back in the 70s by the hand of Bergveld et al. [4] as a device to detect neural activity. Since then, it has also been widely used as a chemical sensor. Very recently, 2D-materials has shown up as promising candidates to implement this kind of sensor, due to their atomic thickness [5], deeply impacting the design and performance of these devices.

Compared with the plethora of experimental results provided by numerous research groups [6, 7], the activities carried out to develop analytical and numerical approaches able to describe these devices have been quite limited [8, 9]. In the case of pH sensing, previous studies only consider the chemical reactions between the sensing interface and protons, neglecting the impact of other reactions in the adsorption of hydrogen ions. In order to assess the impact of these additional surface chemical reactions, we have integrated the generalised approach presented in [10, 11] in our numerical simulator. This allowed us to evaluate the impact of the adsorption of chlorine ions.

II. Self-consistent simulation of 2D-ISFETs

The semiconductor device and electrolyte models are combined for the numerical simulation of the whole device [12]. We solve the 2D Poisson equation using the corresponding model to obtain the charge in each region.

A. Semiconductor device modelling

In the semiconductor region we consider a diffusive transport [13]. Under equilibrium conditions, the electron (hole) density profile, n_L (p_L), is calculated using the 2D density of states. The data in equilibrium is then used to solve the non-equilibrium situation. In that case, n_L (p_L) is calculated using the 1D Drift-Diffusion transport equation.

B. Electrolyte and sensing interface modelling

Regarding the electrolyte region, the local concentration of the i -th ion is related with the potential by the equation:

$$c_i = \frac{c_{i,0} \exp\left(-V_{PMF,i} - \frac{qz_i(V - V_{Ref})}{k_B T}\right)}{1 - 2 \frac{c_{i,0}}{c_{max,i}} \left(1 - \cosh\left(q|z_i| \frac{V - V_{Ref}}{k_B T}\right)\right)}$$

where $c_{i,0}$ is the bulk concentration, z_i the valence, $c_{max,i}$ the maximum allowed concentration and $V_{PMF,i}$ is the PMF profile. The latter is combined with a non-constant water permittivity profile at the device - electrolyte interface. The parameters required for these models are extracted from [2, 3]. As for the reactions taking place at the sensing interface, we integrate the approach reported in [10, 11]. Each reaction is defined by a simple relation between the active element concentration f_i and the product concentration, f_j :

Once the concentrations of the different elements are obtained, the net charge of a surface with an active site density N_s can be calculated as:

$$Q_{net} = N_s \sum_i z_i f_i$$

The reactions considered in the Site-Binding (SB) model and its extended version (eSB) are depicted in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1 Reactions considered in the SB model (a) and its extended version (b). The material of the sensing layer is indicated as M , K_a and K_b are the reactions constant, $[H^+] = 10^{-pH}$ is the hydrogen ion concentration near the interface, $[H^+]_0$ is the bulk hydrogen concentration and $[Cl^-]$ is the chlorine concentration near the interface.

III. Results

A. Site-Binding results

First we take into account only the adsorption of hydrogen ions. The structure considered, as depicted in **Fig. 2**, is a 100nm long MoS_2 based device.

Fig. 2 Structure of the device considered in the simulations. The channel is defined by a monolayer MoS_2 semiconductor sandwiched between a SiO_2 layer and an Al_2O_3 layer, which acts as active layer where hydrogen ions are absorbed (see inset).

The channel is sandwiched between a 20nm-thick SiO_2 layer, which acts as substrate, and a 5nm-thick Al_2O_3 layer acting as a sensing layer. The electrolyte considered is based on KCl along with NaOH and HCl, the concentration of which

change according to the pH. We assume pH values ranging from 4 up to 10, along with four different KCl concentrations, [KCl]: 10mM, 50mM, 100mM and 500mM.

Figure. 3 depicts the sensor transfer characteristic, which shows a decrement of the threshold voltage V_{th} as the pH is reduced: the lower the pH, the higher the concentration of positive H^+ ions, and thus the lower the potential required to switch the potential required to switch on the device. To evaluate the influence of KCl, we calculate the change in the current ΔJ with respect to the minimum concentration [KCl] = 10mM, **Fig. 3** (right). The maximum values of ΔJ are quite low compared with the values of J . The results show an interesting feature with pH as ΔJ changes from negative to positive at pH = 8. This can be associated to the characteristics of the active layer, as it shows a neutral charge for $V_{FG} = 0V$ at that pH value.

Fig. 3 Sensor J - V_{FG} curves for [KCl]= 10mM using the SB model (left) and increment of current when [KCl] is increased (right).

B. Modified Site-Binding results

Once the sensor response has been evaluated by using the SB model, we consider its extended version where the adsorption of chlorine ions is included. The results obtained for that scenario are depicted in **Fig. 4**. The differences with respect to the previous results (**Fig. 3**) are quite evident. The magnitude of ΔJ is almost seven times larger and the trend with V_{FG} is monotonic, i.e. there is not a change in the ΔJ sign showing that the current always decreases as [KCl] increases, independently of the pH considered. This is consistent with the additional reaction considered in the model: the chlorine ions generate a negative charge in the active layer that reduces the amount of the electrons in the channel. Moreover, the higher the concentration of these ions, the more acute is this effect.

Fig. 4 Sensor J - V_{FG} curves for [KCl]= 10mM using the eSB model (left) and ΔJ when [KCl] is increased (right). Dotted lines show the previous results with the SB model.

V. Discussion and conclusions

In this work we have evaluated the transfer response of a MoS_2 FET based pH sensor making use of two models for the active layer. The first model only considers the adsorption of

hydrogen ions, while the second one includes an additional reaction concerning the adsorption of chlorine ions.

Our results show relevant differences when using the two models revealing the importance of side reactions in the modelling of chemical sensors. When the basic SB model is considered, the increase of KCl concentration does not strongly impact the current of the device. Once the side reactions are included through the eSB model, the impact of these changes in [KCl] is much greater: as the concentration of chlorine ions increases, the output current notably diminishes. These changes make possible to obtain the same response by either increasing the pH or the KCl concentration. Looking into this, we can conclude that it is critical to take this effect into account when analysing pH sensors, due to the “crosstalk” between hydrogen and chlorine ions adsorption.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the financial support from the Spanish Government under projects TEC2017-89955-P (MINECO / AEI / FEDER, UE) and EQC2018-004963-P (MINECO / AEI / FEDER, UE), and the European Commission under H2020 project WASP (contract no. 825213). A. Toral-López acknowledges the FPU program (FPU16/04043). E. G. Marín acknowledges Juan de la Cierva Incorporación IJCI-2017-32297 (MINECO/AEI).

References

- [1] F. Pittino et al., “Models for the use of commercial TCAD in the analysis of silicon-based integrated biosensors”, *Solid-State Electronics, Elsevier BV*, **2014**, *98*, 63-69.
- [2] N. Schwierz et al., “Reversed Anionic Hofmeister Series: The Interplay of Surface Charge and Surface Polarity”, *Langmuir, American Chemical Society (ACS)*, **2010**, *26*, 7370-7379.
- [3] N. Schwierz et al., “Anionic and Cationic Hofmeister Effects on Hydrophobic and Hydrophilic Surfaces”, *Langmuir, American Chemical Society (ACS)*, **2013**, *29*, 2602-2614
- [4] P. Bergveld, “Development of an Ion-Sensitive Solid-State Device for Neurophysiological Measurements”, *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)*, **1970**, *BME-17*, 70-71.
- [5] D. Sarkar et al., “ MoS_2 Field-Effect Transistor for Next-Generation Label-Free Biosensors”, *ACS Nano, American Chemical Society (ACS)*, **2014**, *8*, 3992-4003.
- [6] P. Ang et al., “Solution-Gated Epitaxial Graphene as pH Sensor”, *Journal of the American Chemical Society, American Chemical Society (ACS)*, **2008**, *130*, 14392-14393
- [7] M. Lee et al., “Apparent pH sensitivity of solution-gated graphene transistors”, *Nanoscale, Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC)*, **2015**, *7*, 7540-7544.
- [8] R. Narang et al., “Analytical Model of pH sensing Characteristics of Junctionless Silicon on Insulator ISFET” *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)*, **2017**, *64*, 1742-1750.
- [9] A. Shadman et al., “Monolayer MoS_2 and WSe_2 Double Gate Field Effect Transistor as Super Nernst pH sensor and Nanobiosensor”, *Sensing and Bio-Sensing Research, Elsevier BV*, **2016**, *11*, 45-51
- [10] L. J. Mele et al., “General Approach to Model the Surface Charge Induced by Multiple Surface Chemical Reactions in Potentiometric FET Sensors”, *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)*, **2020**, *67*, 1149-1156
- [11] L.J. Mele et al., “A Model of the Interface Charge and Chemical Noise due to Surface Reactions in Ion Sensitive FETs”, *Proc. of SISPAD*, **2019**, 978-1-7281-0939-8; 343 - 346.
- [12] A. Toral-Lopez et al., “Assessment of three electrolyte-molecule electrostatic interaction models for 2D material based BioFETs”, *Nanoscale, Advances, Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC)*, **2019**, *1*, 1077-1085.
- [13] A. Toral-Lopez et al., “GFET asymmetric transfer response analysis through access region resistances”, *Nanomaterials, MDPI AG*, **2019**, *9*, 1027.